

ENDO-RS: Endoskeleton Robotic Serpent for Intelligent Structure Inspection

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Abstract—For search-and-rescue purposes, snake robots provide a unique and useful mobility platform. An example of a bio-inspired platform is the snake-like robot, which is a mechanism designed to move like a biological snake. A snake-like endoskeleton robot with a built-in capability for serpentine movement, as well as machine vision capabilities, is proposed for development in this paper with the purpose of proposing the design and development of the robot. A prototype robot was constructed from eleven sequentially printed segments. Snake robots are continuously deformable, lightweight, modular, and low cost robotic devices that are constructed from multiple joints that are continuously connected. In order to determine the necessary torques for each motor, Matlab’s Multibody Mechanics tool is used. As a result of this simulation, a parametrized virtual model of the robot is created, where rectilinear gaits are programmed. It has been found that a robot with different frequencies, angular positions, and wave lengths (duty cycle) may take different times to reach a target trajectory or end point based on simulation and experimental results. Therefore, the simulation tests are highly similar to the tests conducted on the prototype endoskeleton. For the purpose of inspection and maintenance, the robot is equipped with machine vision capabilities that enable it to detect faults within structures. In addition, we propose a model-reverence adaptive control method based on Lyapunov stability analysis and MIT rules. Using the designed trajectory tracking control law, the multi-joint snake-like robot can track the trajectory of its front joint whenever disturbances are encountered and stabilize its angular position and velocity when disturbances occur as a result of the disturbances encountered. In addition, YOLOv5 has been implemented as the primary object detection model for cracks in structures, and the model has been trained on over 2400 images with an overall accuracy of 94.2%.

Index Terms—Snake, robotics, Design, simulation, machine vision, control, Serpentine, Stability

I. INTRODUCTION

ROBOTIC snakes represent an ideal robotic platform for search- and-rescue applications, as well as tasks in constrained and hazardous environments. The simple structure of the snake body has the capability to traverse complex, constrained, 3-D environments. Snakes are capable of fitting through small gaps, moving over rough terrain, and climbing shear inclines, all of which are useful to navigate the dense undergrowth of a forest or the wreckage of a collapsed building [1]. A range of snake robots have been developed

using traditional robotic kinematics comprising rigid links and discrete joints [2] [3]. The author in the aforementioned reference developed a 3-D origami robotic snake that is able to locomote using lateral undulation and sidewinding gaits similar to those used by biological snakes. In [7], he presented the first mathematical analysis of snake locomotion methods, which described all the forces involved in snake movement. As a result, a plane curve whose curvature varies sinusoidally was proposed to approximate the shape of a biological snake during lateral undulation [4] [5]. Furthermore, soft pneumatic actuators also have disadvantages. They can be inefficient, constantly venting their motive pressure to the environment. In addition, the compressors required to generate the input pressure used in pneumatic actuators tend to be heavy and bulky, reducing the effectiveness of this type of actuation for autonomous mobile robotic applications. Prior work focused on developing soft pressure-operated robotic snakes [6], [7]. These soft robotic snakes use pneumatic pressure to actuate silicone rubber segments that make up the body of the snake, resulting in a constant-curvature deformation along the length of each segment. This results in a flexible, safe, and realistic motion, effectively mimicking the gait of a biological snake [8] [9]. In addition to their ability to move efficiently in unstructured environments, such as narrow pipes, rough or soft ground, or even liquids, snake-like robots are able to imitate snake locomotion in an effective manner. Due to their high degree of freedom, snake-like robots are difficult to control [10]. It is common to find robots with eel-like or snake-like design features as well as lifelike movement, such as those in [11] [10]. In addition to being hyper-redundant devices, snake-like robots are also capable of rotating in multiple directions, thus obtaining many degrees of freedom, although they are notoriously difficult to control [12]. These mechanisms are advantageous because they allow the use of long and flexible bodies in environments that humans are unable to access easily, such as unfamiliar and complex environments.

In spite of the foregoing, there is a growing trend in the literature to optimize snake robot locomotion for terrain of all kinds [13]. Due to this, gait modes based on these animals’ biological behaviors have been developed. In addition to lateral undulations and serpentine gaits, concertina gaits have been studied [14]; rectilinear gaits have been studied [15]; and sidewinds have been studied [16]. Furthermore, some researchers have developed new movement modes for these robots, aimed at improving their locomotion efficiency, including fusion gaits [17], lateral rolling and helix [18], and obstacle-assisted locomotion [19]. Furthermore, the CPG mechanism can also be used to simulate a natural snake’s

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rhythmic crawling motion. Many studies have been conducted on snake-like robot locomotion controlled by CPG with an intelligent control approach, including those described in [20] and [21]. Moreover, Ha et. al. [22], proposed a robotic snake locomotion with force and body tension measurements. A continuum snake model was presented by the author. In addition, the deflection due to body compliance and uniform body tension naturally produces the contact distributions required for forward and backward locomotion, as well as for sidewinding. In conclusion, a simple control strategy is proposed for a robotic snake locomotion, which has been validated through dynamic simulations and physical experiments. Nonetheless, Yang et. al. [23], presented a 3D fabrication method for a metallic flexible joint for a robot that is similar to a surgical robot. As the author stated, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is performed with the goal of optimizing the design process. Experiments are conducted to further understand the characteristics of the flexible joint, including model estimation, finite element analysis, and experimental validation. An example of a design that can withstand 100 000 full loading cycles is presented. As a final step, different design variations of the proposed method are discussed as well as a multi-section flexible endoscope based on the proposed design. In addition to reducing the cost of manufacturing and assembling a snake-like surgical robot, the proposed flexible joint may also contribute to the development of more sophisticated three-dimensional snake robotic structures with optimized sensing and actuation spaces. In [24], research shows stationary base snake robot system that employs small visual sensor to enhance dark images in confined spaces. The robot design is suitable for very small spaces. However, it lacks to remote mobility and on-site autonomous teleportation.

According to the literature, approaches based on these platforms have contributed significantly to the development of snake robots. In spite of this, these mechanisms still have some specific problems, such as their large size, low speed, and control issues, particularly when applied to a critical environment. This paper aims to contribute to the design of an endoskeleton prototype, specifically the configuration of its joints and the planning of its gait for assessing structure damages and cracks with machine vision capabilities. Following is an outline of the paper: Section II introduces the paper's contribution. Section III outlines the ENDO-RS modeling framework. Section IV showcases the prototype simulation. Section V elucidates the prototype design. Section VI presents the vision-based structure analysis. Section VII discusses the training and validation results. Finally, Section VIII provides the conclusion of the research.

II. CONTRIBUTION

It is essential for the development of designs that exhibit enhanced orientability in the domain of robotics, particularly in contexts requiring intricate manipulations within confined environments, such as nuclear facilities. Even though existing scholarly literature extensively examines the analysis of a number of specific types of robotic snake mechanisms within a generalized operational framework, little attention has been

paid to comprehensively understand the behavior dynamics of these robotic systems as they operate in confined spaces adapted to specific critical tasks. Different approaches to methodological research serve not only to enhance range of motion capabilities, but also to facilitate the expansion of manipulation modalities within restricted spatial environments. Therefore, addressing this lacuna is crucial to guiding the design process towards formulating targeted solutions meticulously optimized to meet the demands of confined space operations and critical task inspections. We have therefore designed and developed a multi-joint endoskeleton machine vision-based robotic snake that can be used to inspect confined spaces in a comprehensive manner. Furthermore, this endoskeleton is equipped with cutting-edge machine vision capabilities. Specifically, the robotic head is designed to feature a three-degree-of-freedom rotational joint. A model reference adaptive control has also been implemented, incorporating a Lyapunov stability analysis for determining the adjustment mechanism. Furthermore, the snake's head section incorporates a machine vision module that allows it to perform critical inspection tasks using the state-of-the-art YOLOV5 model.

III. ENDO-RS MODELLING FRAMEWORK

An endoskeleton robot with snake-like characteristics was developed, consisting of 11 identical modules, as well as customized modules for the head and tail. Additionally, each joint of the snake-like endoskeleton robot has one degree of freedom. It consists of 11 identical modules, as well as customized modules for its head and tail. The axis of rotation of each joint is perpendicular to that of the previous module, which allows one axis of movement. An entire robot structure's kinematics is calculated using geometric notation. In order to illustrate the joint axes of the snake-like robot structure, an outline of the structure is drawn. The z_j -axis is the axis of the j -joint and the x_j -axis is perpendicular common to the z_j and z_{j+1} axes. Fig.1 shows the location of each of these axes. In order to determine the geometric parameters for each of the robot joints, which are described in Table 1, the following factors must be considered:

σ_j : type of joint ($\sigma_j = 0$ if the joint is a rotoid joint; $\sigma_j = 1$ if the joint is a prismatic joint).

α_j : angle between the axes z_{j-1} and z_j corresponding to a rotation around x_{j-1} .

d_j : distance between z_{j-1} and z_j along x_{j-1} .

θ_j : angle between the axes x_{j-1} and x_j corresponding to a rotation around z_j .

r_j : distance between x_{j-1} and x_j along z_j .

The joint angles of the snake robot can be denoted as $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{11}$, and the corresponding joint lengths as d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{11} . Following are the Denavit-Hartenberg parameters for this robot:

Moreover, the rotation matrix R_i^{i+1} from joint i to joint $i+1$ can be illustrated using the Denavit-Hartenberg parameters as:

$$R_i^{i+1} = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_i & -s\theta_i c\alpha_i & s\theta_i s\alpha_i \\ s\theta_i & c\theta_i c\alpha_i & -c\theta_i s\alpha_i \\ 0 & s\alpha_i & c\alpha_i \end{bmatrix},$$

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of joint references

Fig. 2: 3D model of the developed endoskeleton robot

where $c_{\theta_i} = \cos(\theta_i)$, $s_{\theta_i} = \sin(\theta_i)$, $c_{\alpha_i} = \cos(\alpha_i)$, and $s_{\alpha_i} = \sin(\alpha_i)$.

Additionally, The translation matrix D_i^{i+1} from joint i to joint $i + 1$ can be framed using the Denavit-Hartenberg parameters as:

$$D_i^{i+1} = \begin{bmatrix} a_i & \\ -d_i s_{\alpha_i} & \\ d_i c_{\alpha_i} & \end{bmatrix}.$$

The transformation matrix from joint i to joint $i + 1$ can be expressed as:

$$T_i^{i+1} = \begin{bmatrix} R_i^{i+1} & D_i^{i+1} \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Joint	θ_i	a_i	α_i (°)	d_i
1	θ_1	L	0	0
2	θ_2	L	-90	0
3	θ_3	L	0	0
4	θ_4	L	-90	0
5	θ_5	L	0	0
6	θ_6	L	-90	0
7	θ_7	L	0	0
8	θ_8	L	-90	0
9	θ_9	L	0	0
10	θ_{10}	L	-90	0
11	θ_{11}	L	0	0

TABLE I: D-H parameters

As a result of multiplying the transformation matrices from the base of the snake robot to its end effector, we can calculate the transformation matrix from the base to the end effector:

$$T_0^{EE} = T_1^2 \cdot T_2^3 \cdot \dots \cdot T_{10}^{11}.$$

A transformation matrix can be used to determine the position of the leading head T_0^{EE} as follows:

$$P_{EE} = \begin{bmatrix} P_x \\ P_y \\ P_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} T_{0,4}^{EE} \\ T_{1,4}^{EE} \\ T_{2,4}^{EE} \end{bmatrix}.$$

To calculate the Jacobin matrix derivative, let us represent the snake robot's joint angles as follows: $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{11}$, and the corresponding joint lengths as d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{11} .

To compute the transformation matrix from the base of the snake robot to its end effector, you can employ the product of the individual transformation matrices.

$$T_0^{EE} = T_1^2 \cdot T_2^3 \cdot \dots \cdot T_{11}^{11}.$$

Furthermore, The position of the end effector can be determined using a transformation matrix T_0^{EE} as:

$$P_{EE} = \begin{bmatrix} P_x \\ P_y \\ P_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} T_{0,4}^{EE} \\ T_{1,4}^{EE} \\ T_{2,4}^{EE} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The position vector should now be differentiated P_{EE} with regards to the joint angles $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{11}$ to obtain the Jacobian matrix.

The Jacobian matrix J can be represented as:

$$J = \frac{\partial P_{EE}}{\partial \theta} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P_x}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial P_x}{\partial \theta_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial P_x}{\partial \theta_{11}} \\ \frac{\partial P_y}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial P_y}{\partial \theta_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial P_y}{\partial \theta_{11}} \\ \frac{\partial P_z}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial P_z}{\partial \theta_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial P_z}{\partial \theta_{11}} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The Jacobian matrix can be determined using the chain rule as follows:

$$\frac{\partial P_x}{\partial \theta_i} = \frac{\partial T_{0,4}^{EE}}{\partial \theta_i}, \quad \frac{\partial P_y}{\partial \theta_i} = \frac{\partial T_{1,4}^{EE}}{\partial \theta_i}, \quad \frac{\partial P_z}{\partial \theta_i} = \frac{\partial T_{2,4}^{EE}}{\partial \theta_i}.$$

The elements of the Jacobian matrix can be calculated by finding out the the partial derivatives of T_i^{i+1} with respect to θ_i . To ascertain the components of the Jacobian matrix, we combine them through matrix multiplication. Conversely, snake endoskeleton robots must possess the ability to transition between various gait modes to adeptly navigate challenging environments. These movements can be depicted as sine waves traversing the body: one for horizontal motion and another for potential vertical motion, as shown in Eq. 12:

$$\alpha(n, t) = \begin{cases} A_x * \sin(\omega_x t + n * \delta_x), & n = \text{odd} \\ A_y * \sin(\omega_y t + n * \delta_y + \phi), & n = \text{even} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where n is the servo motor joint number, A_x and A_y are the amplitudes of the wave, δ_x and δ_y is the spatial frequency, ω_x and ω_y represents the temporal frequency, and ϕ the horizontal and vertical planes. Phase difference refers to the difference in phase between sine waves. This paper will not consider unnatural gait modes, but rather serpentine wavelet motions that allow the robot to adapt to motion with one degree of freedom. Figure 10 illustrates the variables associated with the implementation of the gait mode.

Fig. 3: Lyapunov stability around equilibrium

IV. SERPENT PROTOTYPE SIMULATION

To simulate the robot in a multibody fashion, Matlab-Simulink software is utilized alongside the SimScape tool, facilitating the rapid and efficient calculation of the equations of motion for any mechanical system. Simulation enables the assessment of whether the chosen parameters for the equations of motion yield the intended outcomes. Consequently, model debugging can be conducted within the simulation environment, mitigating the risk of unexpected motions or motor overload. The "World frame" block represents the virtual orientation and positioning structure, while a 6-degree-of-freedom joint (6-DOF-1) establishes the global reference frame, thereby determining the robot's initial position based on the global reference of the system. The system comprises eleven bodies, including the tail and head as depicted in Fig. 10, interconnected with each other. Additionally, each body block includes rotational joints with output signals that indicate the position and torque of the linkage. Furthermore, the rotations and translations of the axes for each link are specified within blocks named "Transform.". Furthermore, during simulation, the robot's interaction with the ground is modeled using asymmetric friction by using a larger normal friction coefficient μ_N and a smaller tangential friction coefficient μ_T . In order to achieve this type of friction model, each link of the snake-like robot is equipped with

two passive wheels. Robot joints are equipped with rotational actuators that allow the robot to move from side to side in a similar fashion to the behavior of a snake in the wild.

Fig. 4: Simulink model

Depending on the design of the inspection environment, the quantity of S-shapes, joint velocity, and inspection area will vary, necessitating a variety of configurations in order to accommodate diverse locomotion patterns. As indicated by the aforementioned analysis, adjustments are made to the parameters of the gait equation by varying their values in order to achieve desired motion characteristics. Moreover, the curvature of locomotion for the snake-like robot adjusts in response to the driving input u , resulting in serpentine motion as depicted in Fig. 10. Several experiments have been conducted to verify the method of modulating motion speed

Fig. 5: Angular position for first three joints

Fig. 6: Angular velocity

Fig. 7: Optimal simulation: Serpentine locomotion at different frequency and angular position

Fig. 8: Real-time experimental trajectories

by altering the frequency of locomotion. The motion velocity of the snake-like robot fluctuates due to three factors, despite maintaining consistent curvature and S-shape as shown in the

Fig. 9: Control simulations: Lyapunov vs. MIT rule

figure above.

There is a similarity between the shape of a snake and that of a Serpenoid curve spreading in the plane. As a result, we can fit the Serpenoid curve to the body of the snake-like robot. As a result, a snake-like robot can be controlled. Various serpentine curves are shown in Figure 10. The following function is defined by [25]:

$$\kappa(s) = -\frac{2K_n\pi\alpha_0}{L} \sin\left(\frac{2K_n\pi}{L}s_p\right) \quad (2)$$

Assuming s represents the distance moved along the axial direction, K_n denotes the number of periods, α_0 signifies the initial angle, L stands for the overall length of the snake robot, and s_p indicates the length of the snake robot along the curve. As the snake-like robot moves, it continues to conform to the shape of the Serpenoid curve spreading in the plane. By integrating equation 11, the relative joint angle of the snake-like robot can be determined. In the snake-like robot's design, the joints are modular, with each joint possessing the same length. We can assume the length of a joint is $l_i = l$, where i ranges from 1 to $n - 1$, representing the sequence number of the joint. Consequently, the overall length of the snake-like robot is given by $L = nl$, where n represents the number of joints. Thus, we can calculate the relative angle between adjacent joints by employing the integral form of the curvature equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_i(s) &= \int_{s+s_{p_{i-1}}+\frac{1}{2}l}^{s+s_{p_i}+\frac{1}{2}l} \kappa(u)du = \int_{s+(i-1)l+\frac{1}{2}l}^{s+il+\frac{1}{2}l} \kappa(u)du \\ &= -2\alpha_0 \sin\left(\frac{K_n\pi}{n}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2K_n\pi}{L}s + \frac{2K_n\pi}{n}i\right) + K_1l \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The parameter K_1 denotes the deflective curvature. Adjusting the value of K_1 allows for the alteration of the direction of

Fig. 10: Dynamic simulation and experimental under different configurations based on parameters change

motion of the snake-like robot. Within the Serpenoid curve, the variable s signifies the axial distance traversed by the snake-like robot.

Based on the derivative of the angles of the joints, we can derive the joint angular velocity $\dot{\theta}$ and angular acceleration $\ddot{\theta}$. $\dot{\theta}$ is a function of s and \dot{s} ; $\ddot{\theta}$ is a function of s , \dot{s} , and \ddot{s} . They are expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\theta}_i(s, \dot{s}) &= -\frac{4K_n\pi}{L}\alpha_0 \sin\left(\frac{K_n\pi}{n}\right) \cos\left(\frac{2K_n\pi}{L}s + \frac{2K_n\pi}{n}i\right) \dot{s} \\ \ddot{\theta}_i(s, \dot{s}, \ddot{s}) &= -\frac{4K_n\pi}{L}\alpha_0 \sin\left(\frac{K_n\pi}{n}\right) \cos\left(\frac{2K_n\pi}{L}s + \frac{2K_n\pi}{n}i\right) \ddot{s} \\ &\quad + \frac{8K_n^2\pi^2}{L^2}\alpha_0 \sin\left(\frac{K_n\pi}{n}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2K_n\pi}{L}s + \frac{2K_n\pi}{n}i\right) \dot{s}^2\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

where \dot{s} and \ddot{s} represent the robot's velocity and acceleration, respectively. Equation 11 can be expressed in Cartesian coordinates as follows:

$$x(s) = \int_0^s \cos(\xi_\sigma) d\sigma \quad (5)$$

$$y(s) = \int_0^s \sin(\xi_\sigma) d\sigma \quad (6)$$

where $\xi_\sigma = a \cos(b\sigma) + c\sigma$, with a as a constant determining the amplitude of the Serpentine curve, b as a constant determining the cycle number of the Serpentine curve, and c as a constant determining the moving direction of the Serpentine curve. Serpentine curves mimic the motion curve of snakes, wherein the surface's curvature continuously changes as it advances at a certain speed. However, the robot's mechanical structure comprises modular rigid joints, limiting its ability to change continuously. Hence, Serpentine curves are discretized into multiple segments, with segment lengths matching joint lengths. Assuming the overall length of the snake-like robot as L , and dividing it into n equally sized segments, each segment's length becomes L/n , equating to the length of a joint. The distance from the first joint to the i -th joint is iL/n , where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Subsequently, equations 7 and 8 can be expressed as:

$$x_i = \sum_{k=1}^i \frac{L}{n} \cos\left[a \cos\left(\frac{kb}{n}\right) + \frac{kc}{n}\right] \quad (7)$$

$$y_i = \sum_{k=1}^i \frac{L}{n} \sin\left[a \cos\left(\frac{kb}{n}\right) + \frac{kc}{n}\right] \quad (8)$$

Moreover, the point (x_i, y_i) ($i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$) is the intersection point of link i and link $i + 1$. Moreover, it is

Assuming that the angle between link i and the motion direction of the snake-like robot is denoted by ϕ_i for $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$, the following equation can be readily obtained:

$$\begin{aligned}\tan \phi_i &= \frac{y_i - y_{i-1}}{x_i - x_{i-1}} = \frac{\sin\left[a \cos\left(\frac{ib}{n}\right) + \frac{ic}{n}\right]}{\cos\left[a \cos\left(\frac{ib}{n}\right) + \frac{ic}{n}\right]} \\ &= \tan\left(a \cos\left(\frac{ib}{n}\right) + \frac{ic}{n}\right) \quad (i = 0, 1, \dots, n)\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

Therefore, the angle between each link and its motion directions can be expressed as:

$$\phi_i = a \cos\left(\frac{ib}{n}\right) + \frac{ic}{n} \quad (10)$$

To analyze the robot's gait, it's crucial to consider the angle θ_i between adjacent joints, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_i &= \phi_i - \phi_{i+1} = \alpha \sin\left(i\beta + \frac{\beta}{2}\right) + \gamma \\ i &= 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

where $\alpha = 2a \sin(b/2n)$ represents the joint amplitude, $\beta = b/n$ denotes the phase difference between adjacent joints, and $\gamma = -c/n$ signifies the parameter controlling the direction of motion. Utilizing the Serpentine curve gait, the robot advances with angular velocity ω . To investigate Lyapunov stability as depicted in Fig. 3, the state of the robot snake is denoted as $x = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{11}]$, where x_i represents the angle of the i -th joint. The following sinusoidal wave equation describes the dynamics of the robot snake:

$$\dot{x} = f(x) = A \sin(\omega t + \phi) \quad (12)$$

Where A represents the amplitude, ω signifies the angular frequency, t denotes time, and ϕ indicates the phase shift. This equation allows us to depict the joints' motion over time in a sinusoidal pattern. Our objective is to discover a Lyapunov function $V(x)$ that fulfills specific conditions to conduct a Lyapunov stability analysis. Let's consider the following candidate Lyapunov function:

$$V(x) = \frac{1}{2}x^T P x \quad (13)$$

Where P represents a positive definite matrix. The derivative of $V(x)$ along the system trajectories is expressed as:

$$\dot{V}(x) = x^T P \dot{x} \quad (14)$$

Given the sinusoidal dynamics governing the robot snake's joints as described by $\dot{x} = A \sin(\omega t + \phi)$, we can delve into stability analysis by linearizing around an equilibrium point. Considering the sinusoidal motion, it's crucial to recognize that equilibrium points occur at specific phases where the derivative of the sine function is zero, i.e., when $\omega t + \phi = k\pi$ (where k is an integer). The system momentarily halts at these points before reversing direction. To conduct stability analysis via linearization:

(1): Identification of equilibrium points: Solve $\dot{x} = A \sin(\omega t + \phi) = 0$ to determine x values where the joints temporarily cease movement (equilibrium points).

(2): Linearization of dynamics: Near these equilibrium points, linearize the system by considering small deviations (δx) from the equilibrium:

$$\delta \dot{x} \approx f'(x_{eq}) \cdot \delta x \quad (15)$$

Where $f'(x_{eq})$ denotes the derivative of $f(x)$ evaluated at the equilibrium point. (3): Eigenvalue calculation (System Poles): Determine the eigenvalues of the linearized system to

Fig. 11: Overview of the proposed testbed showing head on the left and joint section and trail is showing on the right side with power distribution board and controller

Fig. 12: Snake locomotion with respect to reference trajectory

assess its stability. The equilibrium point is deemed stable if all eigenvalues possess negative real parts. Conversely, the equilibrium point is considered unstable if any eigenvalue has a positive real part. To establish the stability of the system around equilibrium, the Lyapunov adjustment mechanism is employed and validated, confirming the system's stability around the equilibrium point.

Fig. 13: Prototype snake mechanism of 2D joint structure

V. PROTOTYPE DESIGN

The robot comprises 11 identical modules for each body link, along with customized head and tail modules. Various types of drives, including pneumatics, electric motors, servos, or wheels, can propel a snake robot. For this project, high torque servo motors were chosen. This selection was made to optimize torque performance, ensuring efficient operation throughout the robot's movements.

To meet the required torque, the SG-90 pro servo motor was chosen. The control system allows for torque speed adjustment and responsiveness to position, load, and angular speed feedback, simplifying integration with a control system. This servomotor reference has a maximum current of 2.5 amps per motor. With a maximum total requirement of 22 amps to

Fig. 14: The proposed testbed is depicted on the right side, with the machine vision module oriented upward for surface inspection. On the left side, various configurations with adjustable amplitudes and frequencies are shown. The diagram below illustrates the real-time motion detection of various room boundaries and edges using the M8 lidar. The 3D mapping, further enhanced by the primary author of this paper, offers a comprehensive view of the environment.

operate the robot, a 30-amp power supply is employed. A snake robot module was designed and fabricated using Fusion 360 software. Figures 10 and 2 illustrate the modules as rotational joints with one degree of freedom. These modules are interconnected, aligning the axis of rotation perpendicularly and allowing for rotation within a range of $+180^\circ$ to -180° . Presently, the design comprises a head module, a tail module, and 11 symmetrical modules, which can be adjusted to suit

specific applications. Table II provides details on the robot's physical dimensions. Additionally, an RPI4 was utilized for machine vision analysis, executing the object detection and segmentation model. An Arduino Mega controls the serpentine locomotion. Due to the slippery nature of the contact between the bare motor and the ground, the lower body of each motor was covered with insulation tape to enhance traction/friction.

Fig. 15: Schematic description of joint values with series connection and the main robotic modules

Numbers of joints	Num = 11
Length of robot	$L = 1.2m$
Total weight	$W = 2KG$
Length of link	$L_{link} = 120 \text{ cm}$
Weight of link	$M_{link} = 0.2 \text{ kg}$
Width of wheel	$L_{wheel} = 8 \text{ mm}$
Radius of wheel	$R_{wheel} = 8 \text{ mm}$
Weight of wheel	$M_{wheel} = 0.08 \text{ kg}$
Friction coefficients	$\mu_N = 0.47\mu_T = 0.025$

TABLE II: Physical parameters of the experimental robot

VI. VISION-BASED STRUCTURE CRACKS DETECTION FRAMEWORK

This paper employs the state-of-the-art YOLOv5 for object detection using the robotic snake camera module. YOLOv5 stands out for its enhanced accuracy and efficiency compared to earlier versions, as well as its user-friendly interface and adaptability. This algorithm combines the features of YOLOv1 to YOLOv4 versions and has been further refined in terms of detection speed and accuracy, making it a widely adopted solution in target detection applications [26]. YOLOv5 operates by employing a single neural network to predict bounding boxes and class probabilities directly from full images in one evaluation, hence its "you only look once" moniker. YOLOv5 offers different variants, ranging from YOLOv5s (small) to YOLOv5x (extra large), each balancing speed and accuracy differently. Smaller models prioritize speed over accuracy, while larger models achieve higher accuracy albeit at the expense of speed. Additionally, YOLOv5 boasts smaller

mean weight files, shorter training times, and faster inference speeds with only a slight reduction in detection accuracy. The YOLOv5 network architecture comprises four main components: Input, Backbone, Neck, and Head. Input involves Mosaic data augmentation, adaptive anchor box calculation, and adaptive image scaling. Mosaic data augmentation stitches four images together through random scaling, cropping, and arrangement to enhance background and small target detection robustness. Adaptive anchor box calculation updates network parameters iteratively to optimize anchor box information based on predicted and real boxes comparison. Adaptive image scaling uniformly scales the original image to a standard size by adding black edges. The Backbone includes Focus and CSP structures. Focus structure quadruples the channel of the image, halves the width and length, and obtains the feature map after convolution. CSP structure splits data into two parts, applies convolution to one part, and concatenates the results with the unprocessed part, thereby reducing memory consumption and enhancing CNN's learning ability. Neck integrates feature pyramid networks (FPN) and path aggregation network (PAN) modules. FPN layer conveys semantic features from top to bottom, while PAN transmits localization features from bottom to top, enriching the model's feature information. Head outputs a tensor comprising object class probabilities, scores, and bounding box information through three detection layers. The model structure of YOLOv5 is depicted in Fig. 16, where the green cube symbolizes modules fused with the CSP structure. $C3_1$, $C3_2$, $C3_3$, and $C3_4$ contain different

configurations of BottleNeck1 and BottleNeck2 modules. In target detection, commonly used evaluation metrics include precision (P), recall rate (R), average precision (AP), and mean Average Precision (mAP). Their calculation formulas are as follows:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (17)$$

$$AP = \int_0^1 P(R)d(R) \quad (18)$$

$$mAP = \frac{\sum_1^n \int_0^1 P(R)dR}{n} \quad (19)$$

$$F1 = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (20)$$

Among these metrics, TP represents the count of accurately detected corn and weeds; FP represents the count of erroneously classified instances of corn and weeds; FN represents the count of missed corn and weeds; and AP represents the area under the precision-recall (PR) curve. A higher AP value indicates superior performance of the target detection algorithm. The mAP signifies the average AP across multiple categories, offering a measure of the algorithm’s overall detection performance across different categories. For model training, the hardware and software platform configuration included the following settings in Google Colab: TPU4, 50GB Memory, Windows 10 operating system, CUDA version 10.2, Python version 3.7, and PyTorch version 1.10. In the experiment, the initial learning rate was set to 0.01, with a final learning rate of 0.2. The momentum parameter was set to 0.937, and the weight decay parameter was set to 0.0005.

To mitigate the early-stage overfitting of the model with small data batches and prevent model oscillation, thus preserving the deep stability of the model.

VII. TRAINING AND VALIDATION RESULTS ANALYSIS

For vision-based capabilities, we have selected a case study focusing on structural health analysis concerning various types of concrete cracks. The dataset comprises over 2400 images, and manual annotation using an annotation tool was conducted to establish the ground truth for subsequent training. Annotation information was formatted in the YOLO dataset format, categorizing the damages into four classes: (1) bullet impact, (2) explosion impact, (3) normal crack, and (4) severe crack. The dataset was partitioned into training, validation, and test sets, maintaining a ratio of 8:1:1, with no data overlap among the sets. All experiments in this study were conducted within the hardware and software environment outlined in Table III. Furthermore, we defined several key hyperparameters for training, including training steps, warmup epochs, warmup initial momentum, batch size, optimization algorithm, initial learning rate, momentum, and weight decay. The specific hyperparameter settings are detailed in Table IV.

Parameter	Resources
Operating System	Google Colab (Linux)
Central Processing	V100GPU
GPU memory	3.12 GHz
Disk	139.42GB
Framework	PyTorch 1.9 .0
Programming language	Python 3.8

TABLE III: Configuration parameters

Model Parameters	Value
training steps	200 epochs
warmup epoch	3
warmup initial momentum	0.8
batch size during training	16
batch size during testing	1
optimization algorithm	SGD
initial learning rate	0.01
momentum	0.94
weight decay	0.0004

TABLE IV: Parameters of the model

The primary focus of this paper is to assess the localization accuracy of objects and the rate of missed or false detections. Common performance metrics are utilized to gauge the efficacy of the enhanced model. These metrics encompass precision, recall, mean Average Precision (mAP), F1 score, number of parameters, Frames Per Second (FPS), among others. To obtain the final experimental results, pre-trained weights are employed to train the model, followed by testing on the designated test set. Particularly, mAP serves as a key metric for evaluating object recognition accuracy, representing the average accuracy achieved across various categories. A higher mAP value indicates superior overall detection performance and enhanced model accuracy. The calculation of average precision is expressed by the following formula:

$$mAP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n AP_i \quad (21)$$

Frames Per Second (FPS) denotes the speed at which the algorithm detects and processes images. If each image takes t seconds to process, the calculation can be expressed using the following formula:

$$FPS = \frac{1}{t} \quad (22)$$

In the context of the object detection model, a higher Frames Per Second (FPS) indicates reduced latency, signifying superior real-time performance and faster computational speed. The model’s efficiency improves as the FPS increases. The obtained results indicate a precision curve of the model at 94.2%, with the train box loss nearing 0.02, and the train object loss at 0.006. The precision metrics range between 80% to 65%, with some variations across classes, while the recall metric stands at approximately 68%. On the other hand, the validation box loss is below 0.035, and the validation object loss ranges between 0.0075 and 0.0080. Additionally, the mean Average Precision (mAP) is 67%, with the precision curve for all classes at 94.2% and the F1 confidence curve at 67%. The precision-recall curve stands at 69.5% at mAP at 0.5, while the

Fig. 16: Yolov5 architecture [27]

R curve is at 87%. These values could be enhanced through parameter tuning, yet the results demonstrate the model's effective prediction of all crack types. The model's training process spans over 4 hours, covering 2400 images. Moreover, Fig. 17 illustrates four plot graphs. The precision-recall curve is a common evaluation metric used in object detection tasks, including YOLOv5, depicting the precision against recall at different confidence thresholds. The F1 curve is a widely used metric in classification tasks, including object detection, to evaluate model performance. The recall curve indicates the model's ability to detect relevant objects in the scene, with higher recall indicating detection of a larger proportion of actual objects present in the images. Fig. 18 presents the loss, mAP, and recall curves for training and validation. The mAP score, obtained by averaging all class Average Precisions, provides a single scalar value representing the overall model performance across all classes. Furthermore, Fig. 19 describes the performance of a classification model on a set of test data where the true values are known. Two sub-figures represent the Correlogram of the training set class count with class distribution and correlation between different class predictions. Fig. 20 displays part of the model code running in the training session with corresponding loss and mAP values. Finally, Fig. 21 and Fig. 22 represent the training and validation results for batch 0, 1, and 2, respectively.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This research paper presents the development of an intelligent endoskeleton serpentine robot with machine vision capabilities. The proposed locomotion is controlled using an advanced adaptive control engineering approach. Servomotors were utilized for constructing the robot, enabling daisy-chaining and serial communication. Initially, a simulation of the robot was conducted in the Matlab-Simulink environment, employing the SimScape multi-body program to test the initial model with its mathematical equations and determine the required torques for the motors. Subsequently, both simulation and real-world tests were performed on the serpentine locomotion mode. The results revealed two notable behaviors: the similarity between simulation and real-world tests, and the satisfactory performance of the real robot in short runs, despite minor deviation errors caused by the need to energetically drag the energy source. Model Reference Adaptive Control (MRAC) employed two adjustment mechanisms: Lyapunov and MIT rules, ensuring smooth control of the first two modules using injected disturbances as a control approach. Furthermore, the study utilized a YOLOv5 model to detect various types of cracks in concrete structures in complex field environments, mounted on the snake endoskeleton robotic system. Initially, over 2400 images were collected, and the dataset was constructed using data enhancement methods

Fig. 17: Precision and recall curves

Fig. 18: Loss, mAP and recall metrics

Fig. 19: Confusion matrix

Epoch	GPU_mem	box_loss	obj_loss	cls_loss	Instances	Size
143/199	3.12G	0.0211	0.006871	0.005496	43	416: 100% 398/398 [00:40<00:00, 9.86it/s]
Class	Images	Instances	P	R	mAP50	mAP50-95: 100% 5/5 [00:01<00:00, 2.51it/s]
all	276	764	0.664	0.7	0.689	0.459
Epoch	GPU_mem	box_loss	obj_loss	cls_loss	Instances	Size
144/199	3.12G	0.02047	0.006734	0.005466	39	416: 100% 398/398 [00:39<00:00, 9.97it/s]
Class	Images	Instances	P	R	mAP50	mAP50-95: 100% 5/5 [00:01<00:00, 2.62it/s]
all	276	764	0.664	0.701	0.689	0.461
Epoch	GPU_mem	box_loss	obj_loss	cls_loss	Instances	Size
145/199	3.12G	0.02101	0.006838	0.00552	103	416: 100% 398/398 [00:39<00:00, 9.96it/s]
Class	Images	Instances	P	R	mAP50	mAP50-95: 100% 5/5 [00:01<00:00, 2.63it/s]
all	276	764	0.665	0.699	0.689	0.46
Epoch	GPU_mem	box_loss	obj_loss	cls_loss	Instances	Size
146/199	3.12G	0.02062	0.006641	0.005475	53	416: 100% 398/398 [00:40<00:00, 9.92it/s]
Class	Images	Instances	P	R	mAP50	mAP50-95: 100% 5/5 [00:01<00:00, 2.66it/s]
all	276	764	0.668	0.688	0.689	0.46
Epoch	GPU_mem	box_loss	obj_loss	cls_loss	Instances	Size
147/199	3.12G	0.02108	0.006713	0.0053	47	416: 100% 398/398 [00:40<00:00, 9.93it/s]
Class	Images	Instances	P	R	mAP50	mAP50-95: 100% 5/5 [00:01<00:00, 2.68it/s]
all	276	764	0.667	0.687	0.689	0.459
Epoch	GPU_mem	box_loss	obj_loss	cls_loss	Instances	Size
148/199	3.12G	0.0207	0.006571	0.005454	100	416: 54% 214/398 [00:21<00:18, 9.91it/s]

Fig. 20: Snapshot of the model while running training session for 200 Epochs

Fig. 21: Training phase results: Batch 0, 1 and 2

Fig. 22: Validation phase results: Batch 0, 1 and 2

focusing on category balance and agronomic characteristics. The results demonstrate the robotic system's effectiveness in precisely identifying critical structure cracks, validating the superior recognition performance of the YOLOv5 model in field conditions. The model can be further improved by adjusting prediction layers with added neuron dropouts and increasing the number of epochs to 400. In future research, efforts will be directed towards enhancing model parameters and structure to achieve a high precision rate, along with modifications to the endoskeleton structure to accommodate smaller critical confined spaces.

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